

TEMPERATURE SENSOR BASED ON LIQUID PHASE TRANSITION

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INTRODUCTION

How to provide a temperature with alarm function for thermal monitoring and trigger temperature indicating?

Cross-sensitivity of piezoresistive materials

temperature signal → strain stimulus

Reversible actuator systems

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EXPERIMENT

Fabrication of the chamber-like sensor device

Figure 1. Preparation process of CNFs/ecoflex films and assembly of the CNFs/ecoflex sensor device.

CONCLUSION

- A temperature sensor with alarm function based on the liquid phase transition is developed.
- Serving as temperature sensor with a TCR at $-0.84\%/^{\circ}\text{C}$ (twice as that of a Pt thermistor and high linearity at 0.999).
- The chamber-like sensor device also showed promising capacity as a temperature alarm with great reversibility.
- The trigger temperature of the alarm sensor could be adjusted via refilling liquids with different boiling points.

RESULT & DISCUSSION

Morphology and sensing performance of CNF/ecoflex film

Figure 2 (a) Typical SEM images of CNFs/ecoflex film. (c) Relative resistance variation of CNFs/ecoflex film under stretching.

- Uniform dispersion and good contact indicates the high conductivity;
- High stretchability allows CNFs/ecoflex film to deform and transfer temperature condition into strain stimulus.

Performance of sensor devices as a temperature alarm

Figure 3. Schematic diagrams of the CNFs/ecoflex sensor device at room temperature (a) and the boiling point of water (b). The relative resistance variation of CNFs/ecoflex sensor devices (film thickness: 0.72 mm) upon heating (c) and in the cyclic test (d).

- Serving as temperature sensor with a TCR at $-0.84\%/^{\circ}\text{C}$ (twice as that of a Pt thermistor) and high linearity at 0.999;
- Closed to the boiling temperature, significant resistance change indicated the potential as an alarm system;
- Similar trade in all cycles indicates good repeatability.